

JURISPRUDENCE

CONTEMPORARY CHALLENGES OF THE SOCIAL HOUSING FUND AND ITS LEGAL REGULATION

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Abstract

The scientific research article "Contemporary Challenges of the Social Housing Fund and its Legal Regulation" discusses the implemented housing reform using the example of Georgia, a country in the post-Soviet space. Within this context, concrete and effective steps have already been taken to replace the dilapidated residential houses inherited from the Soviet era. The reform presents an opportunity to create a necessary social housing fund for various vulnerable groups in the country.

The article focuses on several key areas: a historical overview of the allocation of the housing fund, modern challenges, peculiarities of the municipal housing policy, an assessment of the need for the social housing fund, and a review of international experiences in its renewal. At the end of the article, the relevant aspects of the project to replace dilapidated multi-apartment residential houses are summarized as an important basis for creating a housing fund. The conclusion presents significant recommendations for effectively addressing the above-mentioned issues.

Keywords: housing reform, social housing fund, dilapidated apartment building

1. Introduction

After the collapse of the Soviet Union, in the process of transition to a market economic system, a radical reform of ownership began, which included the process of aggressive privatization carried out by the state both in the direction of housing and land funds.¹ However, it should be noted that the stage of alienation of state property was based on the legacy of Soviet constructions. At the beginning of the 1990s, socialist countries changed the ownership system, which meant the transition from communal, common ownership to individual ownership, in the mentioned process great importance was given to promoting and encouraging the role of individual ownership. American researchers talk about the "tragedy of the common property" when discussing the collective property of socialist countries because they believe that in this system of property, individual needs were denied and owners did not have equal rights to common property objects.² To meet the minimum household needs of the urban working class, active constructions began in the 1950s. The so-called "Khrushovki" is a famous business card of Soviet architecture. The above-mentioned type of apartments are 3-5-story multi-apartment residential houses of the Nikita Khrushchev period, which are a complex of

paneled or brick residential apartments. Microdistricts were developed with this type of residential house. Even though the main architect of these residential houses was Vitaly Lagutenko, they are still referred to as "Khrushovkas".³

The collapse of the Soviet Union and the transition to a new economic formation, like other fields, caused fundamental changes in the field of urban planning.⁴ "Access to housing as part of the standard of living was recognized as a primary human right in 1948."⁵

The service life of the houses built during the Soviet period has passed long ago, in addition, the ongoing military operations in the history of Georgia as an independent country have given rise to a large flow of internally displaced persons, to which a certain number of eco-migrants have also been added, as a result compact settlements have been created at the expense of existing administrative buildings in municipalities, which do not respond to the applicable construction standards.

Establishing a social housing fund in the country is a necessary condition for overcoming housing challenges, especially for the population with special

¹ Jokhadze Kh. 2008. Contradictory nature of nationalization of state property in Georgia. Tbilisi state university. thesis. Tbilisi: Tbilisi University Publishing House, p. 10;

² Hage J., Akkermann B. 2014. Introduction to Law. London: Springer, P.74;

³ Jorbenadze S. 1973. Housing house and of citizens Housing Rights - Duties, Tbilisi: Soviet Georgia, p.32;

⁴ Zazanashvili, N. (2017). Lost in Translation: Housing, Housing or Housing Policy? p. 2;

⁵ Covenant on Social, Economic and Cultural Rights, 1994, p. 5.

needs. The creation of a social housing fund and its rational disposal will have a positive effect on several significant factors:

- ✓ housing shortage will be eliminated;
- ✓ Decent housing will become available for various vulnerable groups (low-income families, elderly, disabled persons, etc.);
- ✓ Ensuring equal access to housing is the most important measure in the way of promoting social equality;
- ✓ Proper urban planning is important in the process of developing municipalities, which ensures the integration of affordable housing into city development plans, prevents the exclusion of low-income populations, and promotes the formation of mixed-income neighborhoods;
- ✓ Within the framework of the social housing fund, the construction of multi-apartment residential houses is possible in close cooperation with the private sector, at the expense of sharing their social responsibility;
- ✓ Equal access to decent living conditions, in a positive context, affects a person's physical and mental health.
- ✓ Modern construction standards are focused on environmental benefits, where the construction of the work within the framework of the social housing fund will be energy efficient and environmentally sustainable.

Fund strategies should be tailored to meet the specific needs of different populations and regions within the country. Establishing a social housing fund is a strategically sound approach to solving housing challenges, promoting social equity, and overall economic and social well-being.

2. Segregation of the State Housing Fund - a historical excursion

In Georgia, at the beginning of the sixties of the Soviet Union, within the framework of the development of the housing sector, thanks to the creation of a new form of housing construction - housing-construction cooperatives, millions of citizens were able to become the owners of an apartment⁶. During this period, a warrant was issued as a document confirming the ownership of the apartment, where the information about the identity of the owner and the family members living with him and their kinship was indicated.⁷

The Soviet space, the government laid the foundation for the idea of construction cooperatives to pool funds with the interested party as early as the

1920s.⁸ On August 24, 1924, the Decree on "Housing Cooperatives" was adopted, which provided for the involvement of the entire population of the working class. To improve the social situation, to strengthen and develop the housing sector. Housing cooperatives were divided into the following categories: housing-rental cooperatives, which were later called "jackets", workers' housing-construction cooperatives, and city-wide housing-construction cooperatives.⁹ Each member of the cooperative participated in the construction of a cooperative residential house through an individual, mandatory contribution, the so-called "pie".¹⁰

The Soviet Union, before the adoption of the still valid Civil Code, the state massively started the privatization of apartments listed in the housing and cooperative construction fund, for which the so-called "subsidies" ensured the signing of the privatization agreement with the apartment owners. would be handed over to the Bureau of Inventory.¹¹ As a result, instead of only the state, the country received many individual owners within each residential building, which is why it became necessary to introduce a new form of organization for apartment owners.¹²

Since the 1950s, investment in the housing sector was not considered an important development strategy and was evaluated as a "resource drain", "consumer product" and "social cost". According to the original idea, "Khrushovki" should have been a temporary residence designed for 30 years, which would later be replaced by typical residential buildings. It is worth noting the statistics, according to which 54% of the population of the Soviet Union was able to be satisfied during the 12 years of construction of "Khrushovki", which in turn alleviated the existing housing crisis. In terms of urban development, against the background of existing "communal" and "barrack" type of housing, "Khrushovki" type apartments, which had an individual sanitary unit and central heating, were a step forward. The term of operation of this type of residential house was determined for 50 years and it was considered a temporary and most effective measure to eliminate the existing housing shortage since the then Soviet government focused on reducing costs and construction period.¹³

The main characteristic of this type of house was that the ceiling height did not exceed 2.5 meters there was no elevator, and in case of major repairs, the house could last 150 years. However, over time, a different reality appeared, the population began to carry out unauthorized constructions, which over time

⁶ Chanturia L. 2000. Introduction to the general part of civil law of Georgia. Tbilisi: Law, p. 548;

⁷ Jordan C. 2008. Neighbor Law. Berkeley: Consolidated Printers. INC., P. 112;

⁸ Chikvashvili Sh. 1989. Housing law. Tbilisi : Soviet Georgia, p. 38;

⁹ Jorbenadze S. 1973. Housing house and of citizens Housing Rights - Duties , Tbilisi : Soviet Georgia, p.23;

¹⁰ Ninua e . 2010. Fellowship By obligation - legally in relationships . dissertation work . Tbilisi : Tbilisi State University, p. 98;

¹¹ Georgia. Ministry of Construction and Urbanization of Georgia. 1999. Minister's Order: Minister of Urbanization and Construction of Georgia on the Approval of the Standard Regulation of the Territorial Service of Technical Accounting of Local Government, (47, 20.07.1999), Tbilisi: Legislative Gazette;

¹² Jordan C. 2008. Neighbor Law. Berkeley: Consolidated Printers. INC. p. 211;

¹³ Jorbenadze S. 1973. Housing house and of citizens Housing Rights - Duties , Tbilisi : Soviet Georgia, p.33;

contributed to the deepening of the damage to the building.

From the second half of the 1980s, the state's expenditure on housing construction was reduced, since the private sector had more active support in this direction and cooperative constructions were developed.¹⁴

The housing crisis in Georgia began in the 1980s when the number of homeless people increased significantly as a result of natural disasters in the mountainous region, as well as the displaced population left homeless as a result of the war. The housing crisis started in the 90s as a result of the commitments made by the Soviet government to various groups of emigrants and displaced persons.¹⁵

3. Contemporary challenges of the housing fund

Concerning the social housing fund in Georgia, the obligation to conduct active actions and policies, as well as to create a normative base, derives from constitutional reservations and international conventions. According to Article 5, Clause 4 of the Constitution of Georgia: "The state takes care of human health and social protection, providing a living wage and decent housing, protecting the family's well-being. The state supports the citizens in employment. The conditions for ensuring the subsistence minimum are determined by law." According to the first paragraph of Article 25 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights: "Every person has right to have of life such Level, food, clothing, housing, medical care and Required social of service including which necessary himself his and his family of health and prosperity to maintain and right secured let it be unemployment, illness, disability, widowhood, old age or from him independent circumstances due to existence means loss other in the case." According to Article 11 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, the States parties to this Covenant recognize that these rights derive from the personal dignity of a person, therefore, it is the right of every person to have an adequate standard of living, adequate food, clothing and including the apartment. According to Article 16, Clause 2, Sub-Clause "F" of the Local Self-Government Code: "Provision and registration of homeless people with shelter" is the exclusive authority of the self-governing unit, within the framework of which the relevant project is being implemented on the example of Tbilisi Municipality.

It is worth noting that the issue of building or construction on existing buildings is covered by the resolution of Tbilisi Municipality Council of May 24,

2016, N14-39 - "St. "On Approving Rules for Regulation of Use and Development of Tbilisi Municipality Territories", which directly indicates that "construction works Implementation unacceptable Such multi-apartment residential on houses whose of housing height from the floor 2.7 m to the ceiling It is less, no have elevator, which exploitation term Maximum is up to 50 years determined ". Taking into account the mentioned record, today it is practically impossible to carry out any kind of additions and constructions to the "Khrushovki" type apartments.

4. Municipal housing policy in Georgia

According to the Constitution of Georgia, the state is responsible for providing citizens with decent living conditions and protecting the well-being of the family.

The Encyclopedia of Urban Studies defines "housing policy" as a set of government actions to achieve housing goals.¹⁶The task may include the improvement of the quality of the existing housing fund, as well as the implementation of many measures to solve the problem of the homeless.¹⁷In Georgia, the management of the housing system is distributed at the state and municipal levels based on the principle of institutional and territorial decentralization. The municipality is implementing the process of legalizing areas in compact settlements, and various measures have been implemented to promote the development of condominiums. One of the components of the maintenance of the existing housing fund is the promotion of the development of condominiums. From this point of view, competencies are separated between the Municipality's City Hall and the Board.¹⁸

Since 2010, the City Hall of Tbilisi Municipality has approved the compensation program for the residents of dilapidated residential buildings, according to which the board had to evict the people living in the dilapidated building with rent for an indefinite period. Of course, the mentioned offer could not solve the main challenge for the capital's municipality in the process of replacing dilapidated multi-apartment residential buildings and was a temporary measure to create a safe environment for the life and health of residents.

By Resolution N35.50.1312 of December 26, 2012, the instructions for the program for residents of dilapidated and uninhabitable houses in Tbilisi were approved, which was followed by the approval of the rules for the compensation sub-program for residents of dilapidated houses budgeted by the City Council of Tbilisi Municipality in 2015 and 2018. The mentioned programs provided compensation for the rent of the apartment for those persons who had unfit or damaged housing as a result of various conditions and had no other alternative housing space. In addition, the number of beneficiaries who are socially vulnerable or affected

¹⁴ Kemen, J. (2001). Comparative Housing Policy and Welfare: Theorizing the Interdependence, p. 115;

¹⁵ Asabashvili L. Nikolaishvili, G. Zazanashvili N. (2018, 22-113). Housing policy in Georgia on the example of Tbilisi, P.26;

¹⁷ Clapham D, Encyclopedia of urban studies, ed. Ray Hutchison (London: SAGE, 2010), p. 22

¹⁸ Asabashvili L. Nikolaishvili, G. Zazanashvili N. (2018, 22-113). Housing policy in Georgia on the example of Tbilisi, P.32;

by various natural disasters should be taken into account.¹⁹

Municipal housing is also available in the capital, therefore, the standard of using the mentioned service has been created and the circle of people has been defined. It should be noted that social housing is widespread in countries such as Austria, Sweden, and the Netherlands, where more than 30% of the population lives in social housing.²⁰ At the same time, Spain, Ireland, and Croatia are distinguished by a high ownership index, which means that 80% of the population is a private owner of a residential house.²¹

No. 10-48 of May 6, 2022, based on the resolution, to ensure safe urban construction for human life and health and to take care of the appearance of the capital, the conditions and procedure for replacing the damaged multi-apartment residential buildings located in the territory of Tbilisi Municipality were determined. According to the rule, the replacement of a dilapidated house is defined as dismantling and placing a new and sustainable building in its place and/or arranging a public space, so that the property rights and other legal interests of the interested persons are protected. Following subsection "h" of article 2 and paragraph 1 of article 4 of the rule approved by the said resolution, the project implementer - non-entrepreneurial (non-commercial) legal entity of Tbilisi municipality "Tbilisi Development Fund" (S/N 404384974) is carrying out the replacement of damaged houses.²²

5. Housing provision as an institutional reform

Considering the condition of the existing housing fund, the state was forced to take effective steps in the direction of satisfying the interested persons with housing. In addition to the objective reasons of the 90s, the problem of homelessness is related to the expiry of the validity period of the buildings and the unfulfilled obligations of the builders. In addition, the creation of a single database of homeless persons and their gradual satisfaction is actively underway. In parallel with the mentioned processes, the process of legalization of the areas occupied by displaced persons is carried out.

"For the displaced long-term home spaces Privatization represents displaced persons towards State strategy to implement of the government by operational in the plan considered long term Accommodation one to one allow Privatization is a refugee of families temporarily using existing spaces private in the property transmission process, their long-term accommodation and home with space providing for the purpose".²³ The state also undertakes to protect the property rights of the displaced person at his permanent place of residence, accordingly, the state

recognizes the right to restitution of the immovable property left at the permanent place of residence of the displaced person, which is inherited.²⁴ The legislative space created for the protection of the rights of displaced people is the first one, which defines the standard of proper housing, establishes the minimum volumes of housing per the affordability, and creates the possibility of creating a special housing fund. It should be noted that to create decent living conditions within the framework of this program, the construction of modern residential buildings is currently underway in Zugdidi Municipality.

A durable solution is considered to be achieved when internally displaced persons no longer need any specific assistance and protection related to forced displacement and can enjoy their human rights without any discrimination based on their displacement. This is achieved in the following ways: by sustainable reintegration in a permanent place of residence (right of return), by reintegration in places of refuge (local integration), or by resettlement in another part of the country.

A long-term solution to the problems of internally displaced persons is established in the UN guidelines on forced displacement, which is one of the most important documents for determining the rights of displaced persons.

International principles are also considered by Georgian legislation. Before the return of internally displaced persons to their permanent places of residence, the state's priorities are still to provide them with long-term housing and to promote socio-economic integration. Today, the Ministry of IDPs administratively "closes" compact settlements when all IDPs living there are satisfied with long-term housing. This process is carried out in three main forms: 1. Privatization: a compact settlement that is fully privatized and its maintenance is the responsibility of the owners and condominiums already living there; 2. Evacuation: IDPs resettled or temporarily moved elsewhere due to potential or actual demolition of the compact settlement building. The Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development of Georgia or the municipality is responsible for the building; 3. Evacuation: IDPs were transferred to another place by their own will or as part of the program of the Ministry of IDPs, but the compact settlement was not destroyed. The Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development of Georgia or the municipality is responsible for the building. After the compact settlement facility is administratively closed, the building is taken from the database of the Ministry of IDPs, and responsibility for the building returns to the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development of

¹⁹ Asabashvili L. Nikolaishvili, G. Zazanashvili N. (2018, 22-113). Housing policy in Georgia on the example of Tbilisi, P.41;

²⁰ Clarke G. 1992. Commons Sense: Common Property Rights, Efficiency and Institutional Change. London: Oxford University Press , p. 30

²¹ Agrawal A. 2001. Common Property Institutions and Sustainable Governance of Resources. USA. Haven: Pergamon, p. 67;

²² Resolution of the City Council of Tbilisi Municipality. 2022. N10-48 "Regarding the approval of the rules for replacement of multi-apartment residential buildings in distress in the territory of the municipality of Tbilisi";

²³<http://mra.gov.ge/geo/static/2653> [21 . 12. 2023] ;

²⁴ Georgia . of Georgia Parliament . 1996. Law : Georgia occupied from the territories by force displaced of persons - IDPs About (1982-II s , 06/02/2014) p, 5;

Georgia or the municipality. Even if the building is administratively closed by the Ministry of IDPs in the above three forms, often IDPs or other homeless/socially vulnerable people occupy and continue to live in the building, even though they (in the case of IDPs) were offered/they were satisfied with temporary or long-term housing. The Ministry of IDPs uses the term "partial closure" to describe such a situation.²⁵

As for the project to replace dilapidated multi-apartment residential houses, in the process of its implementation, it was necessary to create a new legal act and make some changes to the existing one, for the mentioned project to be effectively implemented in parallel with the protection of property rights and urban development of the city.

The various projects implemented in the territory of the municipality, which ensure access to housing, represent a kind of basis for creating a social housing fund in the municipality of the capital city and, following its example, in the country. The social housing fund is defined as "affordable residential space created with the active participation of the state, intended for persons with special needs. They include groups that cannot meet the demand for decent housing under free market conditions. In the circle of persons to be satisfied with the social housing fund Vulnerable groups may include the homeless, families that do not have a high income, the elderly, people with disabilities, students, women victims of domestic violence, displaced persons, single mothers, and others.²⁶It is a matter of assessment, from the point of view of the sociological situation, the real need of such groups - to be satisfied with apartments. Judging by the analogy of providing apartments to the homeless, the demand for shelter is currently high.

The project to replace the dilapidated multi-apartment residential building is a part of the social housing fund, within which the issue of meeting the needs of vulnerable groups may be discussed in the future. Moreover, legal systematization of the issue is required from a legal point of view. The housing fund in Georgia is not only dilapidated houses. The housing fund includes objects such as unfinished buildings, monuments of cultural heritage, compact settlements, privatization funds, and cooperative building funds.

The procedure for the origin of the right of ownership or the replacement of the object of the existing right includes several legal acts, among them, from the point of view of architectural processing, general procedural issues are reflected in the process of restoration-rehabilitation of cultural heritage monuments, and there is no talk of the need to transform the right of ownership, it is not legally evaluated during the rehabilitation process due to the

change of the object of ownership. Adjustment of the scope of the right. A separate legal act regulates the issues of allocation of the privatized housing fund.

6. Dilapidated buildings as an existential challenge

Dilapidated buildings for various social purposes are an existential challenge for many countries. Around the world, dilapidated and abandoned buildings are even given a literary parallel when they are compared to "silent sentinels" whose old facades hold the stories of a bygone era. Their stories are often as varied as the surviving architectural styles, reflecting economic development and disruption, cultural shifts, and social transformations, reminding us of history, creativity, and development.

Various cities around the world have examples of transforming old abandoned buildings into various high-income tourist destinations. This process is called "revitalization" and in addition to the renovation of old buildings, it has other additional benefits, such as: creating new jobs, strengthening the economy, and improving the quality of life of the local population. The process of "revitalization" involves giving new life to an existing building while maintaining its appearance. For example, the following cities and sites have been revitalized: In Boston, the once bustling Quincy Market. A "revitalization" project has transformed the market into a popular tourist destination with shops, restaurants, and attractions. A former Victorian hotel in London has been transformed into a luxurious, modern hotel with stunning views of the River Thames. The "revitalization" project preserved the building's historic facade and added modern interiors and amenities.²⁷

In different countries of the world, solving the issue of dilapidated buildings, including residential houses, requires a comprehensive and multifaceted approach, which involves both the implementation of government policies the active support of society, and the involvement of the private sector.²⁸In the process of replacing dilapidated houses, attention can be focused on several important aspects, such as the development of relevant legal regulations, improvement of construction standards, financing, the introduction of tax incentives, and obtaining grants and subsidies, which are especially popular in the process of financing buildings with the status of historical or cultural heritage. Encouraging the process of revitalization of abandoned buildings.²⁹The need for conservation of cultural heritage in historical development areas, technical support, which involves electronic posting of information about implemented or ongoing projects and ensuring its availability to all interested persons. It is also important to timely identify

²⁵ Gabrieldidze G., 2017. Tbilisi. Master's thesis, "Socio-economic situation of the displaced population from Tskhinvali Regina" Tbilisi Iv. Javakishvili State University

²⁶ Kalichava K., Social Housing fund will create Mechanisms : thinking legislative arrangement on the concept , Georgian-German journal of comparative law; 11/2022

²⁷ Schmid UC 2005. Real Property Law and Procedure in the European Union – General Report. German, Würzburg, P. 121 ;

²⁸ Kemen, J. (2001). Comparative Housing Policy and Welfare: Theorizing the Interdependence, p . 221

²⁹ Housing policy in Georgia (2016). Retrieved from: <https://urbanreactor.org/>.

damage to buildings and monitor the construction process, verifying its compliance with legal or building technical safety requirements. However, it is important to share best practices among European countries in order to develop effective strategies to solve the problem of dilapidated houses. In order to implement the listed strategies, it is necessary to take into account the specific challenges of the region.

In Georgia, the process of replacing damaged buildings is ongoing both in different districts of the capital and in different municipalities across the country. However, it is worth noting that the process of replacement of dilapidated multi-apartment residential houses and the construction of a new building started in Tbilisi Municipality.

7. International experience of renovation of the housing stock

Georgia is one of the countries in the post-Soviet space, which faced the inevitable necessity to take effective steps to replace the multi-apartment residential buildings built during the Soviet Union. In order to renew the emergency housing fund, the countries of the Soviet space chose different strategies, including Russia, which approved the state strategic plan for the fund renewal. According to the mentioned program, different social groups are defined, which are satisfied with the living space. In addition, in the Russian Federation, the consent of 2/3 of the owners is enough to replace a dilapidated residential house, which was followed by a massive protest by the owners opposing the project.³⁰ In Russia, like Georgia, local municipalities were entrusted with the task of renewing the housing fund. The replacement areas were determined by the municipalities and priority was given to those places where the period of operation of dilapidated houses reaches 78 years and also represents a densely populated residential unit. In order to implement the mentioned project, it is possible to use land resources owned by the state or municipality. According to the existing law in Russia, in the process of replacing a dilapidated house in non-priority areas, a general meeting of owners is held, 2/3 of the votes are required to make a decision, and in case of opposition by the remaining 1/3, the said owners are subject to monetary compensation.

Providing the population with affordable and comfortable housing is considered one of the most priority directions in Belarus. The citizen's right to housing is guaranteed by the Constitution of Belarus, in addition, the Housing Code applies. The state actively implements the construction of a housing fund for free transfer to various social groups or for sale to them on preferential terms.³¹ In addition to the mentioned direction, the country's challenge remains the process of reconstruction of damaged buildings and strengthening works. The authorities think that the mentioned measures are much cheaper than the construction of new buildings. The observation of

"Khrushovki" type residential houses in different countries of the Soviet space showed that after the expiration of the operational period, the strengthening-strengthening works of such buildings are only a temporary measure and not a long-term solution to the problem.

According to the Ministry of Industry and Infrastructure of Kazakhstan, there are more than 3000 dilapidated houses in the country. The State Program of Housing and Communal Development in 2020-2025 envisages a mechanism for renewing the housing fund. The owners are given a replacement space of at least the owned space, but not less than a one-room apartment. The program envisages the existence of small apartments in new projects, which will later be sold for commercial purposes. The cost of construction of a new residential building and the price of apartments for sale per 1 sq.m. are determined by expert assessment.³² Residents of Almaty will be able to live in new residential houses from 2023. The existence of dilapidated houses and ways to replace them remains one of the most pressing issues in the region. It should be noted that 40% of multi-apartment residential buildings have been demolished. Private developers are building 17 apartment buildings. In Kazakhstan, an apartment building plan has been drawn up, which provides for the gradual replacement of dilapidated houses. The process of replacement of dilapidated houses envisages the dismantling of existing dilapidated buildings and the construction of new multi-apartment dwellings, including repair works. The example of Kazakhstan shows that different companies can perform the mentioned works. The mentioned project is implemented with the financing of the state and municipal budgets, the largest share comes from the budget of the local municipality.³³ In addition, strengthening and strengthening works of buildings and inventory of residential buildings are planned, and passports reflecting the current situation will be created, which will give all interested residents the opportunity to familiarize themselves with the technical condition of the building.³⁴ In Georgia, in the example of Tbilisi, the money for the repair of the economy class is spent from the municipal budget, while Kazakhstan considers it possible to find different funds for this event. Since it is necessary for the new apartment given to the owners to provide an opportunity to live in it without interruption, it is unjustified to find the money to be spent on repair works from the private sector.

A total of 2,000,000 sq.m. is planned to be built in Almaty within the framework of the program to replace dilapidated houses. Experts express the opinion that such large-scale constructions, along with solving the problem of replacing dilapidated houses, create the need to redistribute resources and determine their sufficiency.³⁵

The replacement program has had many critics in Kazakhstan. According to their opinion, as a result of new multi-story constructions, the urban balance is

³⁰G. Zazanashvili, 2018, p.36

³¹ there

³² (<https://lsm.kz>, 2022)

³³ (<https://krisha.kz>, 2022)

³⁴ (<https://vlast.kz/novosti/>, 2022)

³⁵ (<https://vlast.kz/novosti/>, 2022)

disturbed, since the new multi-story building requires more land resources, which partially involves the utilization of the surrounding areas.³⁶In addition, the number of public transport will be insufficient, and the movement of private transport will be limited. In Kazakhstan, the dense development of the central areas is observed, which burdens the center and is an obstacle to the urban development of the suburbs. According to critics, chaotically placed high-rise buildings can even change the wind speed and therefore the weather forecast. "Rules for the formation of architectural Appearance and urban planning of the city of Almaty" is a document that determines the coefficients of development, urban development policy, both in densely populated areas and protected areas of historical and cultural monuments.

Redevelopment of run-down areas may be considered as a single sector or as a replacement for individual multi-apartment residential buildings. Negotiations with investors involve the transfer of free land to them, with the purpose of later building complex constructions on it.³⁷

Temporary alternative premises are offered and rented out on a "room-for-room" principle, regardless of their poverty.³⁸Due to the increased demand for apartments, rents in Kazakhstan have tripled in the last 5 years.

The problem of access to a well-furnished home and a comfortable living environment is also acute in the United States of America. This goal was clearly formulated half a century ago in the "Act on Housing".³⁹Protection of the right to housing is very important, from an economic point of view, "in the process of dividing society into layers, where society divides material well-being and opportunities into two extremes - this is a trend that creates larger and larger gaps between the richest and the rest, especially the poorest part of the country's population; produces inequality that has a clear racial overtone and makes it impossible for democracy to exist"⁴⁰ In earlier eras, densely populated urban areas were devastated by cholera epidemics and the Chicago fire of 1871. The result of public response was the adoption of the law on "multi-apartment residential buildings", which laid the foundation for mass construction. Although American living conditions have improved since the nineteenth century, fires caused by faulty electrical wiring are still very common today.⁴¹

In Latin America Similar to the post-Soviet countries, the solution to the housing problem began in the 1950s. If the existing housing in developed countries was a rental relationship, in Latin America the occupied spaces were soon privatized.⁴²The country is familiar with the practice of arbitrarily occupying free land plots. As a result, in the 1990s, massive construction of housing began on low-quality lands located in peripheral areas, which met the minimum requirements. The development of such areas has

limited the possibility of employment, education, free movement, and accessibility for the residents there.⁴³

Brazil The so-called "favelas" of informal settlements have a long history. This term first comes from the beginning of the 19th century. The real problem of similar types of settlements has become a result of large migration from the countryside to the cities.⁴⁴Since 2003, interest in the housing sector has been renewed, and in 2004, the concept of housing fund development was formed. Since 2009, the program "My house is my life" has been started, within the framework of which 2,000,000 square meters were built in two years. Since 2016, the interim government has expressed its desire to continue the program within the scope of the current economic conditions, which has hindered the massive nature of construction.⁴⁵

8. Conclusion

In conclusion, the historical aspects of housing reform in Georgia, as well as issues of modern regulation, were reviewed in the scientific research article. The current program for replacing dilapidated houses should be positively evaluated as an excellent opportunity to create a social housing fund.

The various projects implemented within the municipality, which ensure access to housing, serve as a foundation for creating a social housing fund in the capital city and, by extension, throughout the country. This housing fund aims to meet the demand for decent housing among relevant groups of people in Georgia. Therefore, there is an objective need to create a systematized legal document—the housing code. This code would encompass the aspects of origination, change, and termination of ownership rights, discuss effective mechanisms for realizing the rights of owners of cultural heritage monuments, and outline the rights and duties of residents. It would also take into account the peculiarities of managing and disposing of usable areas. With the adoption of the housing code, it would be possible to eliminate institutional and normative deficits, considering the effective management of owners' associations.

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